

Disease resistance

Fertilizer levels and incidence of bunt disease in rice in India

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The incidence of rice bunt disease or kernel smut caused by *Neovossia horrida* has increased with the introduction of high yielding rice varieties and the stress on fertilizer application. This report deals with the effect of high (100-50-50 kg/ha) and low (50-25-25) doses of NPK fertilizer on bunt incidence in 17 rice varieties tested at the Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. Data on number of grains affected per plant and percentage of bunt-affected panicles (after arcsin transformation) were analyzed.

Differences in both number of affected grains and percentage of affected panicles between fertilizer levels and varieties and their interactions were significant.

At high doses of fertilizer, all varieties except IR506 RP5B, CR44-93, Vijaya, and IR8 had significantly more bunt-affected panicles. Jaya had significantly higher bunt incidence than the other released varieties. CR23-4736 had the highest percentage of bunt-affected

The effect of low levels (L_1)^a and high levels (L_2)^b of fertilization on the number of panicles affected by bunt, number of grains affected per plant, and days to 50% flowering in 17 rice cultures. Kapurthala, India.

Cultivar	Bunt-affected panicles (%)			Affected grains (no./plant)			Days to 50% flowering
	L_1	L_2	L_2-L_1	L_1	L_2	L_2-L_1	
IR506 RP ₂ B	1.45	13.70	12.25*	0.8	7.8	7.0*	105
IR644 RP ₂ B	9.22	23.97	14.75*	5.2	15.4	10.2*	104
IR506 RP ₃ B	2.72	12.17	9.45*	1.8	8.6	6.8*	105
IR506 RP ₅ B	5.55	10.07	4.52	2.2	6.0	3.8*	103
IR506 RP ₅ B	4.75	17.30	12.55*	5.2	14.4	9.2*	103
CR23-4594	17.10	40.35	23.25*	10.6	43.0	32.4*	87
CR23-4736	13.32	50.40	37.08*	7.4	54.6	47.2*	94
CR51-3	19.17	34.35	15.18*	18.6	51.6	33.0*	102
CR82-10	16.77	37.97	21.20*	13.0	45.8	32.8*	105
CR44-93	5.27	9.80	4.53	2.8	11.6	8.6*	98
CR66-56	9.67	38.97	29.30*	5.6	29.0	23.4*	94
9435	4.22	10.17	5.95	1.8	4.4	2.6	90
CR100-32	8.77	37.27	28.50*	6.8	34.4	27.6*	98
IR661-1-1-140-3	10.82	44.95	34.13*	7.6	47.2	39.6*	96
Vijaya	8.45	12.10	3.65	2.2	10.0	7.8*	105
Jaya	25.20	39.42	14.22*	11.0	47.00	36.0*	104
IR8	1.40	8.65	7.25	0.4	5.2	4.8*	105
CD = 5%			8.60	3.62			

^a 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

^b 500-25-25 kg NPK/ha.

panicles. All varieties, except 9435, had significantly more affected grains per plant. CR23-4736 had the largest percentage of affected grains, followed by CR51-3, IR661-1-140-3, Jaya, CR82-10, and CR23-4594.

The varieties 9435, IR506 RP5B, IR8,

and Vijaya had fewer affected grains per plant and lower percentage of affected panicles, suggesting that they might be used in hybridization programs. It is suggested that in the development of bunt-resistant lines, segregating materials be screened at higher fertilizer levels.

Incidence of leaf scald disease on dryland rainfed rice in Liberia

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Leaf scald *Rhynchosporium oryzae* is widely distributed in the humid tropics of West Africa. Although the precise extent of damage from it is not known, regional rice pathologists consider it a potentially destructive disease.

We have observed leaf scald throughout Liberia on both rainfed dryland and

lowland rice; its incidence on dryland rice is higher. The national rice varietal improvement program emphasizes the selection of varieties with low incidence of the disease. Of about 4,000 cultivars evaluated in trials from 1974 to 1976 at Suakoko, none were free from leaf scald; however, Khao Dawk Mali, Tetep, IAC1500, IR4547-6-1-4, IR4547-6-2-5, IR2035-290-2-1-1, and Kanto 15 had lower incidence.

In the 1977 wet season, 156 rice cultivars were compared with recommended variety LAC23 under dryland rainfed conditions at the Central Agricultural Experiment Station,

Suakoko, at two fertility levels (0-0-0 and 40-40-40 kg/ha of NPK) and two spacings (30- and 15-cm rows). The first lot of 100 lines, with LAC23 as the check planted after every 10 lines, was seeded on 13 June 1977; the second lot of 56 lines plus 6 plots of LAC23 were seeded on 23 June 1977. Each cultivar was sown in a 10- × 5-m plot, divided into 4 equal parts of 2.5 × 1.5 m each, to accommodate the fertilizer and spacing treatments.

Cultivars were scored on a scale of 1 to 9 for incidence of leaf scald at the flowering stage, in the four fertilizer × spacing treatments. The incidence of leaf